

India's Role within the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC)

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Introduction:

The period after the Second World War is known as the Cold War era. During this period, the world was divided into two blocs: communist and capitalist. In this situation, the Non-Aligned Movement was formed. Various regional cooperation organizations were also established. These regional organizations can generally be divided into two types. One includes military alliance organizations such as SEATO, Warsaw Pact, NATO, etc., and the second type includes organizations like the European Community, the Arab League, ASEAN, SAARC, OPEC, BRICS, and the Gulf Cooperation Council. Based on the principle of regional cooperation, the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) was formed in 1985. India is also a member state of this organization. Therefore, this research paper attempts to study the nature of India's role in this organization.

Research Methodology:

For the present research, introductory and analytical study methods have been used. The research paper has been written using primary and secondary sources. There may be some limitations of time and scope in this research paper.

Problem Formulation:

- (1) Does the SAARC organization include only Asian and developing nations?

- (2) Were some fundamental provisions overlooked at the SAARC summit in New Delhi?
- (3) Is India's participation in SAARC conferences actively observed?

Research Objectives:

- (1) To study the background of the emergence of SAARC.
- (2) To study the provisions of the SAARC conference held in New Delhi.
- (3) To study India's participation and role in SAARC.

Research Hypotheses:

- (1) SAARC originated among South Asian nations.
- (2) Significant provisions were made from the perspective of Asian nations at the SAARC conference in New Delhi.
- (3) India has always maintained active participation in the SAARC organization.

Background of SAARC:

Since ancient times, India has represented various international organizations at the global level. The SAARC organization was formed globally in 1985. A conference of the heads of state of seven South Asian countries was held on December 7th and 8th, 1985, in Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh. SAARC was established at this conference. This organization was formed by seven nations of South Asia: India, Pakistan,

Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan, Sri Lanka, and Maldives. This organization marked the effective beginning of regional cooperation in global politics in Asia. SAARC is the result of the efforts initiated by the then President of Bangladesh, Ziaur Rahman, in 1977. Between 1977 and 1980, Zia visited India, Pakistan, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. Following these visits, he prepared a document regarding this organization, in which ten points were determined for mutual cooperation. To discuss this document, a meeting of the foreign secretaries of the SAARC countries was held in Colombo in April 1981. Subsequently, three more such meetings were held in Kathmandu (1981), Islamabad (1982), and Dhaka (1983). These continuous meetings significantly accelerated the establishment of SAARC. From these meetings, the following subjects were identified for mutual cooperation: economic and social progress, cultural development, collective self-reliance, agriculture, rural development, telecommunications, meteorology, health, transportation, science and technology, sports, art, and culture. In July 1984, a meeting of the foreign ministers of the SAARC countries was held in the Maldives. Subsequently, in May 1985, another meeting of the Foreign Ministers was held in Thimphu, where it was decided to create SAARC. Accordingly, in December 1985, a summit meeting of the heads of these seven countries was held in Dhaka, laying the foundation for the establishment of SAARC.

Structure of SAARC:

The structure of the SAARC organization includes the heads of government and heads of state of the member nations. There was a provision for them to meet at least once a year. In these meetings, the goals, policies, and work of SAARC would be determined. There would be a Council of Ministers comprising the Foreign Ministers of the member states. This council

would formulate policies, review regional cooperation, explore new avenues of cooperation, and consider matters of common interest. The meetings of the Council of Ministers would be held periodically as needed. SAARC would have a committee of Foreign Secretaries, consisting of the Foreign Secretaries of the member countries. They would oversee and control the work of SAARC, coordinate and cooperate in various activities, pool resources, and determine priorities by exploring financial resources. In addition to this, the SAARC structure would include a technical committee, with one member from each member state. The main function of this committee is to implement the decisions taken by the committee of Foreign Secretaries. SAARC would have a secretariat, which was established in Kathmandu in 1987. Implementing policies, coordinating, controlling, and monitoring various programs are the main functions of the SAARC Secretariat.

Main Objectives of SAARC:

- (1) To promote the welfare and improve the quality of life of the people of South Asia.
- (2) To accelerate economic, social, and cultural progress, and to provide all individuals with the opportunity to live a life of dignity and realize their full potential and skills.
- (3) To strengthen the collective self-reliance of the South Asian nations.
- (4) To understand the problems and issues of the South Asian nations and to build empathy and trust regarding them.
- (5) To increase cooperation and provide mutual assistance among member states in the economic, social, cultural, technical, and scientific fields.
- (6) To enhance cooperation with other developing nations.
- (7) To effectively present common issues of mutual interest on international platforms.

(8) To cooperate with other regional or international organizations having similar objectives.

The credit for setting all the above objectives primarily goes to India, because these objectives were decided at the meeting of Foreign Ministers held in New Delhi in 1983.

SAARC New Delhi Conference (1995):

The eighth SAARC summit was held in Delhi on May 3rd and 4th, 1995. The main focus of this conference was primarily on terrorism and poverty alleviation. The main feature of this conference was the unanimous agreement among all members on the implementation of the South Asian Preferential Trade Agreement (SAPTA). It was also declared that 1995 would be celebrated as the SAARC Year of Poverty Alleviation and 1996 as the SAARC Year of Literacy. The conference was attended by Indian Prime Minister P.V. Narasimha Rao, Begum Khaleda Zia (Bangladesh), King Jigme Wangchuck (Bhutan), M.A. Gayoom (Maldives), Manmohan Adhikari (Nepal), Farooq Ahmed Leghari (Pakistan), and Mrs. Chandrika Kumaratunga (Sri Lanka), among other heads of state. The conference reviewed the work of the SAARC during its first decade and highlighted the areas in which SAARC could make progress in the next decade. India played an active role in this conference by presenting resolutions on the following topics:

Resolutions of the SAARC New Delhi Conference:

(1) Celebrating the completion of a decade of SAARC: The heads of government of the SAARC countries expressed satisfaction with the progress made during the first decade of SAARC and decided to celebrate the completion of the decade at both the joint and individual member levels.

(2) Importance in global politics: The SAARC countries declared that they can become stronger through regional cooperation, which will enable

SAARC to play an important role in global politics.

(3) Consideration of underdeveloped nations: The conference considered developing plans for the development of the least developed countries like Nepal, Maldives, and Bhutan. It was suggested that the rules applicable to these nations in the international arena should also be applied to the South Asian nations.

(4) Environmental protection: Global efforts are necessary for the protection of the environment. For this purpose, efforts should be made at the national, regional, and bilateral levels. Every SAARC nation will strive for this.

(5) Elimination of Terrorism: Concern was expressed at this conference regarding the rise of terrorism. This was because the influence of the LTTE organization in Sri Lanka had increased to such an extent that Chandrika Kumaratunga had to leave the conference midway and return to Sri Lanka.

(6) South Asian Preferential Trade Agreement: It was decided that the necessary procedures for implementing the South Asian Preferential Trade Agreement (SAPTA) would be completed, and the agreement would come into effect from December 8, 1995.

(7) South Asian Free Trade Agreement: Similar to SAPTA, it was decided to consider positively the implementation of the South Asian Free Trade Agreement. The objective of both these agreements was to increase trade among SAARC countries.

(8) Poverty Eradication: The declaration of this conference emphasized poverty eradication. The year 1995 was declared as the Year of Poverty Eradication.

(9) Literacy: It was decided to declare 1996 as the SAARC Literacy Year.

(10) Economic Cooperation: This conference emphasized economic cooperation. For this purpose, it was decided that trade fairs would be organized in each member country.

(11) SAARC Nuclear Weapons Ban Treaty: The heads of SAARC countries demanded a complete ban on nuclear weapons. At this time, discussions were underway in New York regarding nuclear-armed nations not attacking non-nuclear nations. The leaders at the SAARC conference demanded that the leaders at the New York conference give the United Nations a completely democratic structure. This would prevent a few nations from dominating the UN.

(12) Non-Discriminatory System: The SAARC conference expressed faith in the principles of the Non-Aligned Movement. This conference advocated for a global structure based on the rule of law, justice, and equality, where there would be no discrimination of any kind between individuals or nations.

(13) Removal of Trade Barriers: The World Trade Organization (WTO) will benefit developed nations in increasing their trade. No SAARC nation will take any decision against the decisions of this organization that would create difficulties in the global trade and social system. It was demanded that the global economy should be built in an open and fair environment, and that the barriers of import and export taxes should now be broken down.

(14) Climate Research: The heads of the SAARC countries expressed satisfaction over the establishment of the SAARC Documentation Centre (SDC) in New Delhi and the SAARC Meteorological Research Centre (SMRC) in Dhaka. The New Delhi SAARC conference considered the implementation of the South Asian Preferential Trade Agreement (SAPTA). At this conference, the President of Maldives, M. A. Gayoom, stated that all these proposals cannot be implemented until certain conditions are met. Finally, the conference concluded with the decision to hold the ninth SAARC conference in Maldives.

Conclusion:

In this way, India has made timely efforts within the SAARC organization to resolve the important issues facing the nations of the Asian continent. It has also strived to ensure that SAARC nations become nuclear-weapon states and self-sufficient in food grains. India has also initiated discussions on fundamental issues such as terrorism, environmental conservation, economic prosperity, education, and employment. This shows that India has provided effective leadership within the SAARC organization.

- (1) It is observed that the SAARC organization includes only Asian and developing nations.
- (2) It is evident that significant provisions for developing nations were made at the SAARC New Delhi Summit.
- (3) India's active participation in SAARC's functioning is observed.
- (4) India has always played a significant role in the SAARC organization.

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